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Ultrasonic NDE of GdCu, SmCu, GdZn and SmZn intermetallics

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The thermo-acoustical features of rare-earth intermetallics GdCu, SmCu, GdZn and SmZn are investigated in the present work. In the initial step, second order elastic constants (SOECs) of selected intermetallics are determined at room temperature using the formulation based on Brugger's definition of elastic constants considering Coulomb and Born-Mayer type interaction potential among the atoms. Later on, elastic modulus and anisotropy are computed using the SOECs. After that the density of these intermetallics are estimated using their lattice parameters. Finally, the ultrasonic velocity and related physical quantities (specific heat, thermal energy density, thermal relaxation time and thermal conductivity) are calculated. The analysis of obtained data realizes that the mechanical behavior enhances with reduction in lattice parameter and intermetallic GdCu owes comparatively good elasto-ultrasonic features in comparison to the other three intermetallics.

Keywords: Elastic property, rare-earth intermetallics, thermal conductivity, ultrasonic velocity.

Introduction

The material formed with the combination of metal atoms that differ in structure in comparison to the constituent metals is called as intermetallics. The last twenty years, rare-earth metal based CsCl/B2 structured equi-atomic heavy rare-earth intermetallics compounds have a lot of attraction due to their superior elastic, thermal, electrical and magnetic properties in comparison to ordinary metals¹⁻⁷. The excellent strength, ductility and good corrosion resistance properties make them important for industrial applications. Using different theoretical approach, the elastic/mechanical, thermo-dynamical and ultrasonic properties of B2 structured YM (M: Cu, Zn, Ag, Rh)¹⁻⁵, AgRE (RE: Sc, Y, La-Lu)⁶ and REZn (RE: Sc, Y)⁷ intermetallics are reported elsewhere.

The experimental study of pressure dependent structural properties of cubic CsCl structured GdCu, LaAg, NdAg, NdZn, CeZn and LaZn have studied using energy dispersive powder measurements⁸. Acoustic emission and microstructure of GdCu have been measured by Sarusi *et al.*⁹. Elastic and magnetic studies of GdZn single crystal under effect of pressure have been performed by Rouchy *et al.*¹⁰. The structural properties of several Cu and Zn based binary CsCl/B2

structured rare-earth intermetallics have been described in literature¹¹. On the basis of first principle study, Singh *et al.*¹² have investigated the structural, elastic and electronic properties of GdCu and GdZn intermetallics. Compounds GdCu, GdZn, SmCu and SmZn have high ductility and fracture toughness therefore; these have potential applications in aerospace engineering and in manufacture of appliances. In spite of technological importance, very few works have been concentrated for the characterization of these materials. The ultrasonic non-destructive evaluation (NDE) technique is one of the best techniques to explore the inherent properties of the materials. Therefore, the present work is focused on a systematic theoretical study of elastic, ultrasonic and thermo-physical properties of B2 structured GdCu, GdZn, SmCu and SmZn rare-earth intermetallic compounds for their improvement in future applications. Initially, the second order elastic constants (SOECs) are calculated using potential model approach at 300K, which in turn is used for determination of their mechanical and thermo-physical properties. Later on, the velocity of ultrasonic wave are determined for wave propagation along $\langle 100 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$ crystallographic directions. On the basis of obtained results and their analysis, the characteristic features of chosen materials are illustrated.

Theory

Second order elastic constants

According to generalized Hooke's law, the stress acting in a particular direction on the crystalline material can be expanded in terms of strain¹³.

$$X_I = \sum_{i,j=1}^6 C_{ij} \eta_j \quad (1)$$

Where, X_I and η_j are the components of stress and strain respectively while C_{IJ} is known as the SOECs or stiffness constants. The solution of Eq.(1) under the symmetry condition of cubic B2 structured material reduces the 36 types of C_{IJ} to three types as C_{11} , C_{12} , and C_{44} . The elastic energy density (U) is function of components of strain tensor. Therefore, its second order differential with respect to strain provides the SOECs.

$$C_{ij} = \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial \eta_i \partial \eta_j} \quad (2)$$

The elastic energy density at temperature T is sum of energy density at 0 K (U^0) and increase in energy density (vibrational part of energy density: U^V) with enhancement in temperature by amount T . Therefore, the expression of SOECs at finite temperature T becomes as :

$$C_{ij} = \frac{\partial^2 U^0}{\partial \eta_i \partial \eta_j} + \frac{\partial^2 U^V}{\partial \eta_i \partial \eta_j} = C_{ij}^0 + C_{ij}^V \quad (3)$$

Here, C_{ij}^0 and C_{ij}^V are the static and vibrational parts of these SOECs. The elastic energy density at 0 K is function of interaction potential $\phi_{\mu\nu}(R)$ and can be written as:

$$U^0 = (2V_C)^{-1} \sum \phi_{\mu\nu}(r) = (2V_C)^{-1} \sum (\phi_{\mu\nu}^C(r) + \phi_{\mu\nu}^{BM}(r)) \quad (4)$$

Where, V_C is volume of unit cell and r is the distance between v^{th} atom in 0^{th} cell and μ^{th} atom in neighborhood cell. The quantities $\phi_{\mu\nu}^C(r)$ and $\phi_{\mu\nu}^{BM}(r)$ are the Coulomb ($\pm e^2/r$) and Born-Mayer ($A \exp(-r/b)$) interaction potentials between the atoms respectively. Here e is electronic charge, A is constant and b is non-linearity parameter. The unit cell of B2/CsCl structured materials have Cs ion at (0,0,0) and Cl ion at (1/2, 1/2, 1/2) co-ordinates. If unit cell have cube edge of $2r_0$ then its volume becomes as $4(r_0)^3$. Considering central atom/ion positioned at (0,0,0), the number of atom/ions in first and second neighborhoods to the central atom becomes as 8 and 6 respectively whose co-ordinates are $(\pm 1, \pm 1, \pm 1)r_0$, $(\pm 2, 0, 0)r_0$, $(0, \pm 2, 0)r_0$ and $(0, 0, \pm 2)r_0$.

Therefore the first and second nearest neighbor distance becomes as $r_1 = \sqrt{3}r_0$ and $r_2 = 2r_0$ respectively. Considering the interaction up to second nearest neighbors, the differentiation of Eq. (4) provides the expressions of static part of SOECs¹⁴.

$$\left. \begin{aligned} C_{11}^0 &= \frac{3}{8} \frac{e^2}{r_0^4} S_5^{(2)} + \frac{3\phi(r_1)}{br_0} \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{3r_0} + \frac{1}{b} \right) + \frac{2\phi(r_2)}{br_0} \left(\frac{1}{2r_0} + \frac{1}{b} \right) \\ C_{12}^0 = C_{44}^0 &= \frac{3}{8} \frac{e^2}{r_0^4} S_5^{(1,1)} + \frac{\phi(r_2)}{br_0} \left(\frac{1}{2r_0} + \frac{1}{b} \right) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (5)$$

Where, $\phi(r_1) = A \exp(-r_1/b)$, $\phi(r_2) = A \exp(-r_2/b)$, $S_5^{(2)} = 0.354190$, $S_5^{(1,1)} = 0.346708$ and $A = (bZ_0 e^2 / r_0^2) (8\sqrt{3} \exp(-r_1/b) + 12 \exp(-r_2/b))$.

Similarly, vibrational energy density is also function of interaction potential when vibrational energy ($\hbar\omega$) of atoms is comparatively larger than the thermal energy ($k_B T$)¹⁵.

$$U^V = k_B T \sum_{i=1}^{6N} \ln(\hbar\omega / k_B T) \quad (6)$$

Where, k_B , \hbar and ω are the Boltzmann's constant, Planck's constant divided by 2π and angular frequency of vibration ($\omega^2 = (1/6) \sum \Delta \phi_{\mu\nu}(r) / M_v$). Here M is the mass of the v^{th} atom. Since $\Delta(e^2/r) = 0$, therefore only the short range repulsive potential $\phi_{\mu\nu}^{BM}(r)$ will contribute in determination of vibrational energy density. At temperature T , the lattice parameter changes to $r_0 + \delta r$, hence the component of tensor (η_j) becomes as $\delta r / r_0$. On the expansion of Eq. (6), its second order differentiation with respect to strain provides the vibrational part of the SOECs¹⁴.

$$C_{ij}^{Vib} = \left\{ l_1 k_B \left| \frac{\partial C_{ij}^0}{\partial r} \right|_{r=r_0} + \frac{f_{ij}^{Vib}}{TV_C} \right\} T \quad (7)$$

Here, f_i^{Vib} is the vibrational energy per unit cell. V_C is the volume of unit cell l_1 . The physical quantity is function of nearest neighbor distance and corresponding potential function which can be determined by following expressions.

$$\left. \begin{aligned} l_1 &= -r_0 \left[\left\{ \frac{8}{3} (2y_1 + 2y_1^2 - y_1^3) \phi(r_1) \right\} + \left\{ \frac{3}{2} (2y_2 + 2y_2^2 - y_2^3) \phi(r_2) \right\} \right] Y^{-1} \\ Y &= \left[\left\{ \frac{8}{3} (y_1^2 - 2y_1) \phi(r_1) \right\} + \left\{ \frac{3}{2} (y_2^2 - 2y_2) \phi(r_2) \right\} \right] \\ &\quad \times \left[\left\{ \frac{8}{3} (y_1^2 - 2y_1) \phi(r_1) \right\} + \left\{ 2 (y_2^2 - 2y_2) \phi(r_2) \right\} \right] \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (8)$$

Here, y_1 and y_2 have values equal to r_1/b and r_2/b respectively. The SOECs of B2/CsCl structured materials at a finite temperature T can be determined using Eqs. (3), (5) and (7) on the basis of the knowledge of their lattice and non-linearity parameters.

Ultrasonic wave velocity

There are six modes of propagation in crystalline medium as three in optical (1 LO and 2 TO) and three in acoustical (1 LA and 2 TA) region¹⁶. Here O and A stand for optical and acoustical while L and T correspond to longitudinal and transverse modes respectively. The propagation of ultrasonic wave resembles the acoustical mode of propagation as it is a pressure wave. The velocities in these modes (V_L , V_{T1} and V_{T2}) for cubic/B2/CsCl structured materials depend on the SOECs, mass density and direction of propagation which are defined by the expressions given in literature^{1,17}. These studies also describe that both the transverse velocities have same values for wave propagation along axial (<100>) and symmetry (<111>) directions. The volume of unit cell of cubic/B2 structured materials having 'a' lattice parameter is equal to a^3 . If the molecular weight and density of material are M_w and d respectively, then M_w/d volume of material will contain Avogadro numbers of atoms (N_A). Therefore, n atoms will occupy a volume $M_w n'/d N_A$. Comparing volume of unit cell, we found that:

$$d = \frac{M_w n}{N_A a^3} = \frac{M_w n}{8 N_A r_0^3} \quad (9)$$

Where n' is number of atoms per unit cell of the base lattice. Debye average velocity (V_D) is velocity of elastic wave of maximum frequency in crystalline media and is an important parameter in the low temperature physics because it is related to elastic constants through ultrasonic velocities¹⁷.

$$V_D = \left\{ \frac{1}{3} \sum_{i=1}^3 \int \frac{1}{V_i^3} \frac{d\Omega}{4\pi} \right\}^{-1/3} \quad (10)$$

Where, V_i is constituent acoustical velocity in different modes of propagation within the crystalline medium. The temperature corresponding to maximum frequency of phonon that can propagate through crystalline media is termed as Debye temperature. The Debye temperature (T_D) is indirectly related to elastic constants through Debye average velocity¹⁷.

$$T_D = \frac{hV_D (6\pi^2 n_a)^{1/3}}{2\pi k_B} \quad (11)$$

Here, h is Planck's constant; n_a is atom concentration. The specific heat at constant volume (C_V) and thermal energy density (E_0) of the medium is the function of T_D/T and can be determined with help of literature¹⁸. The propagation of ultrasonic wave through crystalline medium is entropy producing process which causes loss of ultrasonic energy. Due to this, thermal distribution of phonon is disturbed on the propagation of ultrasonic wave which is maintained by relaxation mechanism. The re-establishment time of phonons distribution is called as thermal relaxation time (τ) and is given by the following equation¹⁷:

$$\tau = 3 k / C_V V_D^2 \quad (12)$$

Thermal conductivity and Grüneisen parameter of B2/CsCl structured material can be determined with the expressions given in literature^{1,14,19}. The ultrasonic attenuation measures the loss of ultrasonic energy and is directly governed by thermal relaxation time, thermal conductivity (k) and Grüneisen parameter (γ) of the concerned medium¹⁷. Therefore, the relative loss of ultrasonic energy in chosen intermetallics can be understood after determination of thermal conductivity and related parameters.

Results and Discussion

The lattice parameters (a) of chosen rare-earth intermetallics GdCu, SmCu, GdZn and SmZn are taken from literature¹¹ and are listed in Table 1. The non-linearity parameters (b) of the selected intermetallics are determined under equilibrium or minimum energy conditions which are also mentioned in Table 1. The SOECs of GdCu, SmCu, GdZn and SmZn intermetallics are calculated using Eqs. (3), (5), (7) and taking input as lattice and non-linearity parameters. These SOECs are used for the determination of elastic properties such as bulk modulus (B), shear modulus (G), Young's Modulus (Y), Poisson's ratio (σ), Lamé moduli (λ , μ) and anisotropy (A) with help of expressions given in literature^{1,20}. The calculated SOECs and elastic moduli at temperature 300 K are given in Table 1.

It has been reported by Rouchy *et al.*¹⁰ that the values of C_{11} , C_{12} , C_{44} and B of GdZn are 81.5 GPa, 49.2 GPa, 37.6 GPa and 59.9 GPa respectively, while these values are obtained 81.7 GPa, 45.8 GPa, 47.3GPa and 57.2 GPa in present computation. The reported and present values of SOECs and B of GdZn are found to very close each other. Yet, very few studies have been reported for

Table 1 – Lattice parameter, density, SOECs and elastic moduli of GdCu, SmCu, GdZn and SmZn at 300K.

Compounds→ Parameters↓	GdCu	SmCu	GdZn	SmZn
a (Å)	3.505	3.528	3.602	3.627
b (Å)	0.269	0.281	0.425	0.446
d ($gm\ cm^{-3}$)	8.51	8.09	7.91	7.50
M_w (gm)	220.79	213.91	222.63	215.75
C_{11} (GPa)	113.3	108.3	81.7	77.8
C_{12} (GPa)	48.5	47.7	45.8	44.5
C_{44} (GPa)	52.6	51.4	47.3	45.9
Y (GPa)	105.4	101.2	77.9	74.2
B (GPa)	69.4	67.2	57.2	55.0
G or μ (GPa)	42.3	40.5	30.6	29.1
λ (GPa)	41.2	40.2	36.8	35.6
σ	0.247	0.249	0.273	0.275
A	1.62	1.70	2.64	2.76

elastic properties of chosen rare-earth intermetallics however a comparison with literature¹⁰ provides justification for considered theoretical potential model approach for evaluation of elastic parameters. The lattice parameters in chosen intermetallics reduce from GdCu to SmZn (Table 1). The reactivity of metal Cu and lanthanides Gd are larger than transition metal Zn and lanthanide Sm respectively. Hence, intermetallic GdCu shall have strongest interaction force while SmZn shall hold weakest interaction force. This reveals that the reduction of lattice parameters enhances the interaction force among the atoms of crystal lattice. Hence, force per unit area and per unit strain will increase with reduction in lattice parameter. This is the reason behind the decay of elastic constants from GdCu to SmZn (Table 1). Among all the chosen intermetallics, the intermetallic GdCu has highest elastic moduli therefore it will have comparatively better mechanical properties.

If fracture/toughness ratio (B/G) is greater or equal to 1.75 then material will be ductile^{12,20}. The obtained B/G of GdCu, SmCu, GdZn and SmZn are 1.64, 1.66, 1.87 and 1.89 respectively. Therefore, intermetallics GdZn and SmZn will have ductile characteristics while GdCu, SmCu will have brittleness features. It also reveals that GdCu will have more ionic bond than SmZn. The recognition of ionic, covalent and metallic nature of bonding forces can also be done on the basis of Poisson's ratio. The values of Poisson's ratio of complete ionic, covalent and metallic compounds are 0.00, 0.25 and 0.33 respectively. As well as, the bonding forces

among atoms are non-central for $\sigma \sim 0.00-0.25$ and are central for $\sigma \sim 0.25-0.50$ respectively. The present value of Poisson's ratio (Table 1) also indicates that GdZn and SmZn will have less ionic and more covalent bond characteristics whereas GdCu and SmCu will have more ionic and less covalent bond characteristics. The anisotropic feature of crystalline material can be defined on the basis of anisotropic parameter (A). The parameter A is found to increase from GdCu to SmCu (Table 1) therefore, direction dependent property will enhance from GdCu to SmCu.

The densities of GdCu, SmCu, GdZn and SmZn intermetallics are determined with help of Eq.(9) using corresponding lattice parameter. The obtained densities are presented in Table 1. The reported densities of GdCu and GdZn are $8.74\ gm\ cm^{-3}$ and $8.18\ gm\ cm^{-3}$ respectively¹². This justifies our density calculation for the chosen materials. The ultrasonic velocities are evaluated with help of literature for wave propagation along $\langle 100 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$ crystallographic directions^{1,17}. The obtained velocities are used for the determination of Debye average velocity (V_D) with help of Eq.(10). The calculated velocities are shown in Table 2.

The longitudinal ultrasonic velocities are obtained larger than that of shear ultrasonic velocity for each direction of propagation because stiffness constant C_{11} is found greater than C_{12} or C_{44} for all the intermetallics under study. The similar results are also reported for yttrium based rare earth intermetallics¹. Yet, the elastic constants decay from GdCu to SmZn but ultrasonic velocities of SmCu and SmZn are found greater than GdCu and GdZn respectively (Table 2). Therefore, density plays significant role in relative variation of ultrasonic velocities in chosen intermetallics.

Table 2 – Ultrasonic velocities (in $km\ s^{-1}$) and thermal relaxation time (in ps) of GdCu, SmCu, GdZn and SmZn at 300K for wave propagation along $\langle 100 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$ crystallographic directions.

Direction	Compounds→ Parameters↓	GdCu	SmCu	GdZn	SmZn
$\langle 100 \rangle$	V_L	3.649	3.659	3.214	3.221
	V_T	2.486	2.521	2.446	2.473
	V_D	2.709	2.744	2.620	2.644
	τ	61.8	67.5	165.8	174.4
$\langle 111 \rangle$	V_L	4.061	4.106	3.909	3.947
	V_T	2.145	2.148	1.873	1.877
	V_D	2.369	2.373	2.080	2.086
	τ	78.9	88.0	256.6	273.7

The Debye average velocity of chosen intermetallics is found high for wave propagation along $\langle 100 \rangle$ direction and found low for propagation along $\langle 111 \rangle$ direction. Therefore, easy direction of propagation of ultrasonic waves in selected intermetallics is $\langle 100 \rangle$ direction. Hence, the ultrasonic wave will propagate with low obstruction and high speed in these intermetallics along axial direction. Since the number of atom involved in the momentum transfer for wave propagation along axial direction is least than the non-axial direction (symmetry direction) in B2 structured materials therefore due to low energy dissipation and high stiffness along axial direction, the phonon of maximum frequency will propagate with maximum speed. This is reason for maximum V_D along $\langle 100 \rangle$ direction. The similar behavior of V_D is also reported for rare earth intermetallics¹.

The Debye temperature (T_D) are calculated using Eq.(11), which in turn is used in determination of C_V and E_0 . Thermal relaxation time for selected intermetallics is calculated using Eq. (12) and related parameters. The obtained values of τ are depicted in Table 2. The thermal conductivity (k) and Grüneisen parameter (γ) are also determined using literature¹. The obtained values of T_D , C_V , E_0 , k and γ are given in Table 3.

Table 3 – Debye temperature (T_D : K), specific heat at constant volume (C_V : $10^5 \text{ Jm}^{-3}\text{K}^{-1}$), thermal energy density (E_0 : 10^8 Jm^{-3}), Grüneisen parameter (γ) and thermal conductivity (k : W/cmK) of GdCu, SmCu, GdZn and SmZn at 300K.

Compounds→ Parameters↓	GdCu	SmCu	GdZn	SmZn
T_D	290.1	291.8	273.0	273.6
C_V	9.21	9.02	8.54	8.34
E_0	1.98	1.94	1.87	1.82
γ	0.89	0.85	0.47	0.44
k	1.36	1.49	3.16	3.31

Yet, the elastic moduli, ultrasonic velocities, specific heat and thermal energy density is found large for GdCu intermetallics however low thermal conductivity is received for GdCu in comparison to other selected materials. As well as, it is also received that the thermal conductivity follows the trend of lattice parameter of selected intermetallics. It is reported¹⁹ that the lattice part of thermal conductivity at fixed temperature is proportional to molecular weight (M_W), cube of Debye

temperature (T_D^3), atomic volume (δ^3) and γ^{-2} . The molecular weight of GdCu, SmCu, GdZn and SmZn intermetallics are 220.79 g, 213.91 g, 222.63 g and 215.75 g respectively. The order of magnitude of T_D^3/γ^2 of the compounds under study are 3.1×10^7 , 3.4×10^7 , 9.2×10^7 and 11.0×10^7 respectively. Though the physical quantities M_W , T_D and δ of these intermetallics are very close to one among but γ is found to reduce with increase in lattice parameters. Thus the thermal conductivity of chosen intermetallics resembles the trend of T_D^3/γ^2 and is predominantly affected by Grüneisen parameter.

The obtained values of C_V , E_0 and γ are found to resemble the opposite characteristics of lattice parameters for chosen intermetallics. The re-establishment time of intermetallics under study is obtained comparatively large for wave propagation along axial direction in comparison to propagation along direction of symmetry. The quantity V_D is received large for ultrasonic wave propagation along axial direction while is received comparatively small for wave propagation along direction of symmetry. As well as, k is found to follow the nature of lattice parameter of these intermetallics. Therefore, the thermal relaxation time of selected intermetallics in particular direction is mainly governed by thermal conductivity while its direction dependency is affected by Debye average velocity. The obtained value of τ lies between 61.8 ps to 273.7 ps depending upon direction and material. On the other hand, GdCu possesses comparatively low thermal relaxation time for wave propagation along axial direction. The physical quantities τ and k are the governing factors for ultrasonic attenuation¹⁷ at high temperature. Therefore, GdCu intermetallics shall have relatively low loss of ultrasonic energy in comparison to SmCu, GdZn and SmZn intermetallics.

Conclusion

The discussion concludes that our theoretical approach for evaluation of elastic moduli is justified. The elastic and mechanical properties of GdCu are received to be better than SmCu, GdZn and SmZn intermetallics. GdCu intermetallics is found to have high bonding strength, low compressibility, high hardness, large stiffness/elastic moduli, high ultrasonic velocity, low thermal conductivity/thermal relaxation time and low ultrasonic attenuation in comparison to other chosen intermetallics. The obtained results provide a good understanding of elastic, mechanical, thermal and ultrasonic properties

of Gd/Sm based rare-earth intermetallics which may be used not only for further investigation but also in material manufacturing industries.

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